

The Effect Of The Coriolis Force On A Propulsive Element And Performance

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It is known that when a body is subjected to both rotational and translational motion, there exists a force normal to the direction of translation that is called the Coriolis force. Fluids going through propulsive turbomachinery stage experience both rotational and translational motion simultaneously. Consequently, the fluids experience the Coriolis forces. Analytical and computational fluids dynamics work was done to establish the orientation of the Coriolis forces on the axial turbomachinery blade. It was concluded that the Coriolis force acts in the radial direction for axial components, and design improvement implications are discussed for turbomachines with axial leading edge.

Introduction

The kinematics of a propulsive fluid element undergoing a turbomachinery stage is not complete without a rigorous examination of the Coriolis force. Unlike an isolated airfoil, the aerodynamics of turbomachinery also consists of rotational and translational motion. A good understanding of the Coriolis force and how to control its action at the design point of turbomachinery can yield a measurable improvement in performance.

Generally, in propulsion technology a quantified half-percent increase in efficiency can easily translate to millions of dollars in fuel economy for a commercial airline or military aircraft, and space application. This is the underlying justification for this work.

Quasi-analytical and graphical presentations of forces of motion on a blade leading edge are presented. In this paper, a commercial computational fluid dynamics CFD code “ANSYS Flowtran.” was used to qualitatively support the quasi-analytical conclusions. Flowtran solves the momentum equations, conservation of mass, and conservation of energy. The code uses the relationship between the shear stress and the shear rate to generate the solutions of the Navier-Stokes equations for compressible and incompressible flows (2-equation model). The turbulent boundary layer is modeled using the $k-\epsilon$ formulation, along with the log law of the wall. The flow in this study is incompressible, and in a rotating reference frame. The governing equations for the CFD analysis employed by Flowtran are finite difference formulation. Further details on numerical methodology are provided the work of Agboola (1998).

Metzger and Rohrbach (1986) tested NASA’s advanced technology SR-series blades and found that forward sweep increased performance by as much as 1.5%. Metzger and Rohrbach’s SR-2 blade is unswept, and the SR-3 blade has a 34.5° sweep. The author found that the SR-3 blade is about 1.5% more efficient than the SR-2. The reason for the improved performance is discussed in the results and conclusions of this paper. It must be noted that, this paper deliberately did not discuss separation over blade surfaces. Rather, the paper focused on the leading edge and the trailing edge design variations.

Background

Kinematics of Fluid Particles on an Axial Blade Surface

Just like solid mechanics, the motion experienced by fluids is governed by some specific geometric deformations. (*To make discussion from kinematics point of view easy, fluid particles replace fluids*) This motion may be sub-classified as shear stress, strain or elongation, translation, and rotation. It is possible to investigate the motion by taking a closer look at the equation of motion starting from Newton's second law. In equations 1a and 1b, \mathbf{a} is the particle acceleration, \mathbf{F} is the force experienced by the particle with mass m

$$\mathbf{F} = m\mathbf{a} \quad (1a)$$

$$\frac{D\mathbf{V}}{Dt} = \mathbf{a} \quad (1b)$$

$$\rho \frac{D\mathbf{V}}{Dt} = \mathbf{f} = \mathbf{f}_{body} + \mathbf{f}_{surface} \quad (2)$$

For a Newtonian viscous (with a constant μ) and incompressible fluid, the momentum equation is given .

$$\rho \frac{D\mathbf{V}}{Dt} = \rho \mathbf{g} - \nabla p + \mu \nabla^2 \mathbf{V} \quad (3)$$

In the equations given above $D\mathbf{V}/Dt$ is the absolute particle acceleration in the inertial frame of reference \mathbf{XYZ} . If the particle is fixed at a point in space, at a distance to the origin of a local coordinate system xyz , with the particle subjected to angular velocity $\boldsymbol{\Omega}$ about the origin of xyz and velocity \mathbf{V} , respectively, Greenwood (1988) wrote that the absolute acceleration of the particle is given by

$$\mathbf{a} = \frac{D\mathbf{V}}{Dt} = \mathbf{a}_B + \frac{d\boldsymbol{\Omega}}{dt} \times \mathbf{r} + \boldsymbol{\Omega} \times (\boldsymbol{\Omega} \times \mathbf{r}) \quad (4)$$

where \mathbf{a}_B is the absolute acceleration of the origin. Equation 4 is used to obtain expression 5 below

$$\frac{D\mathbf{W}}{Dt} + \boldsymbol{\Omega} \times (\boldsymbol{\Omega} \times \mathbf{r}) + 2\boldsymbol{\Omega} \times \mathbf{W} = -\nabla \frac{p}{\rho} + \frac{\mathbf{F}}{\rho} + \frac{\mu}{\rho} \nabla^2 \mathbf{W} \quad (5)$$

Equation 5 is the general equation of motion of a translating body of fluid relative to a rotating coordinate system, where the second and the third terms in the left-hand side (LHS) are due to the blade rotation. The second term in Equation 5 is the centripetal acceleration term and the third term is the Coriolis acceleration term.

Both Vavra (1960) and Lakshminarayana (1996) showed by illustrations that the Coriolis force is in the radial direction. Anand (1976) wrote about the qualitative nature of turbomachinery flow, that the spanwise migration of the flow produces a thinner boundary layer near the hub, a thicker one at the tip. Adkins and Smith (1982) showed that the spanwise migration of the boundary layer has a considerable influence on the spanwise (radial) mixing of flow, well into the potential flow regime.

From the numerical simulations results, the computed radial, tangential, and axial components of velocity were examined to provide better understanding of radial migration of low momentum fluids.

The analytical tools took the form of kinematics of fluid particles on the axial blade surface, an extension of a previously reviewed topic. In

turbomachinery, it is necessary to go through graphical presentation to make design changes. Therefore, the ensuing analysis integrates graphical methods.

The Coriolis Forces

Rotation of a rigid element about a fixed point:

A small element of fluid C is defined with a particle at point P_c on C . The fluid element C is allowed to rotate about a fixed coordinate system xyz with origin at B . Assuming that the fluid element is frozen or rigid as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Rotation of a rigid element about a fixed point.

$V_{P_c/B}$ is the velocity of P on C relative to B and it is also the absolute velocity of P_c , because it is taken relative to the fixed system xyz . Ω is the

angular speed, and Ω is the absolute angular velocity vector of P_c acting along the positive axis of rotation of C so that $L = s [\sin (\theta)]$.

$$\dot{L} = \frac{\Delta L}{\Delta t} = \Omega s [\sin (\theta)] \quad (6a)$$

$$\mathbf{V}_{P_c/B} = \Omega \times \mathbf{s} \quad (6b)$$

$$\dot{\mathbf{s}} = \mathbf{V}_{P_c/B} \quad (7)$$

The acceleration of P is given by

$$\mathbf{a}_{P_c/B} = \frac{d(\mathbf{V}_{P_c/B})}{dt} = \Omega \times \frac{d\mathbf{s}}{dt} + \frac{d\Omega}{dt} \times \mathbf{s} \quad (8)$$

$$\mathbf{a}_{P_c/B} = \Omega \times \dot{\mathbf{s}} + \dot{\Omega} \times \mathbf{s}$$

Substituting (7) and (6b) into (8)

$$\mathbf{a}_{P_c/B} = \Omega \times (\Omega \times \mathbf{s}) + \dot{\Omega} \times \mathbf{s} \quad (9)$$

The first term in the RHS of (9) is the centripetal acceleration and the second term is the tangential acceleration, all relative to xyz . $\underline{a}_{P_c/B}$ is the absolute acceleration of P_c .

The velocity and acceleration of P on a rigid element in motion:

Point P_c is defined on a rigid body of fluid element C, and C is defined in a moving coordinate system xyz with origin at B. The moving coordinate system xyz , is in turn defined in a non-inertial coordinate system XYZ with origin at A, where B moves with velocity $\mathbf{V}_{B/A}$ relative to the fixed system XYZ , and the fluid element C rotates about B in the xyz system as shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2. The velocity and acceleration of P on a rigid element in motion

$$\mathbf{V} = \mathbf{V}_{P_c/B} + \mathbf{V}_{B/A} = \boldsymbol{\Omega} \times \mathbf{s} + \mathbf{V}_{B/A} \quad (10)$$

\mathbf{V} is the absolute velocity of point P, $\mathbf{V}_{P_c/B}$ is the velocity of point P to point relative B, and $\mathbf{V}_{B/A}$ is the absolute velocity of B

$$\mathbf{a} = \mathbf{a}_{B/A} + \boldsymbol{\Omega} \times (\boldsymbol{\Omega} \times \mathbf{s}) + \dot{\boldsymbol{\Omega}} \times \mathbf{s} \quad (11)$$

The general motion of a fluid particle in a rotating frame of reference:

Figure 3 shows the fluid element C in translation along a path on the rotating system xyz with origin at B, and the non-inertial system XYZ with origin at A. The motion of a particle located at point P_C on the body of fluid C can be tracked and explained with the aid of a coincident point P_B , located in the xyz system. \mathbf{R} is the position vector of B relative to A in the XYZ system, and \mathbf{r} is the position vector of P relative to B in the xyz system. The position vector of P relative to A is \mathbf{S} , so $\mathbf{S} = \mathbf{R} + \mathbf{r}$. As viewed by a fixed (non-rotating) observer located at B, while xyz experiences an angular velocity $\boldsymbol{\Omega}$, the rate of change of \mathbf{r} is given by

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{\mathbf{r}} &= \dot{\mathbf{r}}_{rel} + \boldsymbol{\Omega} \times \mathbf{r} = \dot{\mathbf{r}}_{P_C/B} + \boldsymbol{\Omega} \times \mathbf{r} \\ \dot{\mathbf{r}}_{rel} &= \dot{\mathbf{r}}_{P_C/B} = \mathbf{V}_{P_C/B} \end{aligned} \quad (12)$$

The absolute velocity \mathbf{V} is given by differentiating \mathbf{S} with time and relative to the XYZ system

$$\mathbf{V} = \dot{\mathbf{S}} = \dot{\mathbf{R}} + \dot{\mathbf{r}} = \frac{d(\mathbf{R})}{dt} + \frac{d(\mathbf{r})}{dt} \quad (13)$$

Substituting (12) into (13), gives Equation (14)

$$\mathbf{V} = \dot{\mathbf{R}} + \dot{\mathbf{r}}_{P_C/B} + \boldsymbol{\Omega} \times \mathbf{r} = \frac{d\mathbf{R}}{dt} + \left(\frac{d\mathbf{r}}{dt} \right)_{P_C/B} + \boldsymbol{\Omega} \times \mathbf{r} \quad (14)$$

where

$d\mathbf{R}/dt$ is the absolute velocity of B

$[d\mathbf{r}/dt]_{P_C/B}$ is the velocity of P_C relative to B

$\boldsymbol{\Omega} \times \mathbf{r}$ is the velocity of P_B relative to B

The absolute acceleration of point P is the time derivative of Equation (14)

$$\mathbf{a} = \dot{\mathbf{V}} = \frac{d\dot{\mathbf{R}}}{dt} + \left(\frac{d\dot{\mathbf{r}}}{dt} \right)_{P_C/B} + \frac{d(\boldsymbol{\Omega} \times \mathbf{r})}{dt} \quad (15)$$

Figure 3. The coordinate systems (stationary and moving) showing points P_B and P_C .

$$\frac{d\dot{\mathbf{R}}}{dt} = \ddot{\mathbf{R}} \quad (16)$$

$$\left(\frac{d\dot{\mathbf{r}}}{dt}\right)_{P_C/B} = \ddot{\mathbf{r}}_{P_C/B} + \boldsymbol{\Omega} \times \dot{\mathbf{r}}_{P_C/B} \quad (17)$$

The second expression in the RHS of (17) is the first Coriolis term

$$\frac{d(\boldsymbol{\Omega} \times \mathbf{r})}{dt} = \dot{\boldsymbol{\Omega}} \times \mathbf{r} + \boldsymbol{\Omega} \times \dot{\mathbf{r}} \quad (18)$$

substituting (12) into (18)

$$\frac{d(\boldsymbol{\Omega} \times \mathbf{r})}{dt} = \dot{\boldsymbol{\Omega}} \times \mathbf{r} + \boldsymbol{\Omega} \times \dot{\mathbf{r}}_{P_C/B} + \boldsymbol{\Omega} \times (\boldsymbol{\Omega} \times \mathbf{r}) \quad (19)$$

The second expression in the RHS of (19) is the second Coriolis term. The rearrangement of Equations (12 and 15 through 19) gives a new expression for the absolute acceleration of P.

$$\mathbf{a} = \ddot{\mathbf{R}} + \ddot{\mathbf{r}}_{P_C/B} + \dot{\boldsymbol{\Omega}} \times \mathbf{r} + 2(\boldsymbol{\Omega} \times \dot{\mathbf{r}}_{P_C/B}) + \boldsymbol{\Omega} \times (\boldsymbol{\Omega} \times \mathbf{r}) \quad (20)$$

$$\mathbf{a} = \ddot{\mathbf{R}} + \dot{\mathbf{V}}_{P_C/B} + \dot{\boldsymbol{\Omega}} \times \mathbf{r} + 2(\boldsymbol{\Omega} \times \mathbf{V}_{P_C/B}) + \boldsymbol{\Omega} \times (\boldsymbol{\Omega} \times \mathbf{r})$$

Substituting \mathbf{W} for the relative velocity vector $\mathbf{V}_{P_C/B}$, Equation (20) becomes

$$\boldsymbol{\alpha} = \frac{D\mathbf{V}}{Dt} = \frac{d^2\mathbf{R}}{dt^2} + \frac{d\mathbf{W}}{dt} + \frac{d\boldsymbol{\Omega}}{dt} \times \mathbf{r} + 2(\boldsymbol{\Omega} \times \mathbf{W}) + \boldsymbol{\Omega} \times (\boldsymbol{\Omega} \times \mathbf{r}) \quad (21)$$

$(d^2\mathbf{R}/dt^2)$ is the absolute acceleration of B.

$\{d\boldsymbol{\Omega}/dt \times \mathbf{r} + \boldsymbol{\Omega} \times (\boldsymbol{\Omega} \times \mathbf{r})\}$ is the acceleration of P_c relative to a stationary observer at B.

$(d\boldsymbol{\Omega}/dt \times \mathbf{r})$ and $\{\boldsymbol{\Omega} \times (\boldsymbol{\Omega} \times \mathbf{r})\}$ are the tangential and centripetal accelerations of P_c respectively, from a non-rotating observer at B.

$(d^2\mathbf{R}/dt^2)$, $(d\boldsymbol{\Omega}/dt \times \mathbf{r})$ and $\{\boldsymbol{\Omega} \times (\boldsymbol{\Omega} \times \mathbf{r})\}$ are the absolute acceleration of P_c .

$(d\mathbf{W}/dt)$ is the acceleration of P_c relative to observer moving with the xyz system (of P_c relative to P_B).

$[2(\boldsymbol{\Omega} \times \mathbf{W})]$ is the Coriolis component of acceleration.

The Coriolis acceleration is due to the combination of the change in the direction of the relative velocity in space and the forces exerted through the centripetal acceleration to affect these changes in magnitude and direction (Tyson, 1966). The statement of Coriolis Law is presented by Kepler (1960), Martin (1982), and Greenwood (1988): for any point such as P_c that moves along a rotating path, its absolute acceleration is the vector sum of the following acceleration vectors: the acceleration of point P_c relative to a coincidental point P_B on the path, the absolute acceleration of the point P_c as seen by an observer on the coincidental point P_B on the path. The Coriolis acceleration is normal to the path. The direction of the Coriolis acceleration is perpendicular to the relative velocity vector. Tyson (1966) and Greenwood (1988) presented the Coriolis acceleration from the kinematics of machines' (solid particles) point of view, while Vavra (1960) presented the Coriolis acceleration from the kinematics of turbomachinery flow's (fluid particle's) point of view.

Figures 1, 2, and 3 show the coordinate system, including the Coriolis term. For a turbomachinery fixed to the ground (XYZ system), the displacement vector between (A) and (B) is constant in time (i.e., the origin of the axis of the coordinate system of the rotor is not moving relative to the ground). Therefore, the $(d^2\mathbf{R}/dt^2)$ term is zero. The $(d\boldsymbol{\Omega}/dt \times \mathbf{r})$ term is zero as well, if the angular speed is constant, reducing Equation (21) to the following

Figure 4. Physical significance of the Coriolis force on an axial blade surface.

$$\mathbf{a} = \frac{D\mathbf{V}}{Dt} = \boldsymbol{\Omega} \times (\boldsymbol{\Omega} \times \mathbf{r}) + \frac{d\mathbf{W}}{dt} + 2(\boldsymbol{\Omega} \times \mathbf{W}) \quad (22)$$

Substituting (22) into the Navier-Stokes equation

$$\frac{D\mathbf{W}}{Dt} + \boldsymbol{\Omega} \times (\boldsymbol{\Omega} \times \mathbf{r}) + 2\boldsymbol{\Omega} \times \mathbf{W} = -\nabla \frac{p}{\rho} + \frac{\mathbf{F}}{\rho} + \frac{\mu}{\rho} \nabla^2 \mathbf{W} \quad (5)$$

where in the axial turbomachine

\mathbf{W} is the relative velocity

$(D\mathbf{W}/Dt)$ contains both the local and the advective components of the acceleration

$\{\boldsymbol{\Omega} \times (\boldsymbol{\Omega} \times \mathbf{r})\}$ is the centripetal acceleration, and it is directed towards and perpendicular to the rotor axis

$[2(\boldsymbol{\Omega} \times \mathbf{W})]$ is the Coriolis acceleration

As previously shown, the Coriolis acceleration is derived from two quantities; one $(\boldsymbol{\Omega} \times \mathbf{W})$ from the change in the magnitude and direction of the displacement vector \mathbf{r} due to the effect of rotation; and the other $(\boldsymbol{\Omega} \times \mathbf{W})$ from the angular velocity $(\boldsymbol{\Omega} \times \mathbf{r})$ due to rotation. This provides the basis for determining the sense of the Coriolis force. According to Tyson (1966), the sense of the Coriolis acceleration is determined using the right hand rule, the $(\boldsymbol{\Omega} \times \mathbf{r})$ is crossed into the direction of the relative velocity vector \mathbf{W} . The direction is also taken perpendicular to the axis of rotation (i.e., normal to the angular velocity vector). Another significant consequence of the $(\boldsymbol{\Omega} \times \mathbf{r})$ term is that the force required to overcome the Coriolis acceleration is stronger near the tip than near the hub. This is due to the fact that the Coriolis acceleration is obtained from the substantial derivative of $(\boldsymbol{\Omega} \times \mathbf{r})$ and the second derivative of \mathbf{r} . Whereas \mathbf{r} increases from the blade hub to the tip, one cannot overlook the importance of \mathbf{r} . Figure 4 shows the physical significance of Equation 5. According to Lakshminarayana (1996), the senses of $(D\mathbf{W}/Dt)$, $(\boldsymbol{\Omega})$, and $(\nabla p/\rho)$

vectors of the fluid particle P depend on flow turning, compressibility, rotation, curvature, thickness distribution, blade geometry, and flow geometry including flow angles, incidence, Mach number, Reynolds number, which vary in all directions. For these reasons, the directions of $(D\mathbf{W}/Dt)$, $(\boldsymbol{\Omega})$, and $(\nabla p/\rho)$ are shown only arbitrarily on Figure 4.

Figure 5. The 2-D Coriolis force effect along the three blades' leading edge

Results

The Coriolis effects on the axial rotor surface:

The Coriolis acceleration is of significant importance in turbomachinery applications, where it is only equal to zero if $\boldsymbol{\Omega}$ and \mathbf{W} are parallel. But if \mathbf{W} is

parallel everywhere to the rotation axis, energy transference to (compressor) or from (turbine) the fluid by the rotor will not take place. For increased transference of energy axial components, there must be an increased Coriolis acceleration. This also underscores the importance of the moment of fluid momentum near the leading edge. Anand and Lakshminarayana (1978) showed that the boundary layer is thinner at the hub than at the tip.

Figure 6. The 2-D Coriolis force effect along the three blades' trailing edge.

Lakshminarayana (1996) provided a graphical representation of the Coriolis forces on the surface of an axial compressor, to better explain Vavra's treatise of the subject. Anand and Lakshminarayana explained that due to the Coriolis acceleration three-dimensional effects are introduced in the viscous layer the radial flows introduce additional loss that may decrease

overall performance. There exists interaction between the viscous layer and the inviscid region, and this spanwise flow of low momentum fluid also causes an increase in the radial turbulent intensity with a corresponding decrease in the remaining two components of turbulent intensities. Figure 4 is similar to the graphical representation of the Coriolis acceleration by Vavra and Lakshminarayana for the geometry being discussed in this paper.

It should be noted that the fluid particle P is at an arbitrary location on the blade surface, and that both the leading and the trailing edges are regions of the blade surface. If the fluid particle P in Figure 4 is now moved to the leading edge, as shown in figure 5, a graphical understanding of the Coriolis effect can be illustrated, were the dominant component of Coriolis forces is still in the spanwise or radial direction at the leading edge.

This behavior is supported by the CFD results, with the presence of increasing spanwise velocity gradient from near the hub towards the tip, at the leading edge. This is in agreement with the fact that the boundary layer is thinner at the hub, as was proved by the experimental results of Anand, (1976). Another question arises from the CFD results, why is this spanwise velocity gradient skewed towards the tip? Because in order to have an increased transference of energy, there must be an increased Coriolis acceleration. An increased transference of energy into the working fluid towards the tip exists because the angular velocity ($\mathbf{V}_t = \mathbf{U} = \boldsymbol{\Omega} \times \mathbf{r}$) is linearly proportional to blade radius r and the radius increases from hub to tip. It should also be noted that $[2(\boldsymbol{\Omega} \times \mathbf{W})]$ is the sum of two quantities derived from the substantive derivative (the derivative following the motion) of $(\boldsymbol{\Omega} \times \mathbf{r})$, and the second derivative of (\mathbf{r}) . Therefore, the Coriolis acceleration is due to the combination of the change in the direction of the relative velocity in space

and the forces exerted through the centripetal acceleration to affect these changes in magnitude and direction (Tyson, 1966). In the absence of separation and all other adverse effects, the fluid in the potential field just ahead of the leading edge experiences stagnation, reducing the advection of the particles by the mean flow. Thus the spanwise Coriolis effect is easily drawn into the potential field as well. Adkins and Smith (1982) and Wisler et al. (1987) found that the boundary layer has a considerable influence on the flow mixing, well into the potential flow regime.

Figures 5 and 6 show the three blade models (forward swept, unswept, and rearward swept) plotted in two dimensions with the Coriolis acceleration shown. In Figure 5, the particle P is placed at the leading edge of each blade. In Figure 6, the particle P is placed at the trailing edge of each blade. If the spanwise migration of fluid is represented by the directions of the Coriolis acceleration, the effect of blade sweep becomes apparent. The natural migration path of the boundary layer, along the leading edge is truncated as suggested by Wright and Simmons (1990). The upward radial migration of low momentum fluid, along the leading edge, is impeded by the curvature of the forward swept blade as shown in Figure 5. The rearward swept blade's leading edge cannot impede the spanwise movement of the fluid because the blade curves away from the particle. At the trailing edge the combination of advective forces and turbulent mixing, due to trailing edge wake, is strong enough to interrupt the spanwise migration of fluid. According to Figure 6, it can also be said that the motion of the particle P into the wake of the blade is aided by the trailing edge's movement away from the particle. Therefore, there was no particulate build up at the trailing edge. The CFD results are presented in figures 7, 8, and 9. Figure 8 shows the unswept rotor blades and Figure 9 the rearward swept blades. These two results from the unswept and the rearward swept blades show the presence of increasing spanwise

velocity gradient from the hub towards the tip. This is the Coriolis effect along the blade leading edge. On the other hand, Figure 7 shows that the positive radial migration of fluid is retarded, as predicted by the kinematics of fluid particles along the blade leading edge surface.

Figure 7. The passage exterior radial velocity result for the forward sweep, flow is right to left.

The spanwise migration of low momentum fluid is retarded as shown in Figure 7. Mohammed and Raj (1977) found that swept blade fans operate more efficiently. Metzger and Rohrbach (1986) tested NASA's advanced technology SR-series blades and found that forward sweep increased performance by as much as 1.5%. Metzger and Rohrbach's SR-2 blade is unswept, and the SR-3 blade has a 34.5° sweep. The author found that the SR-3 blade is about 1.5% more efficient than the SR-2.

Figure 8. The passage exterior radial velocity for the no- sweep, flow is right to left.

Figure 9. The passage exterior radial velocity for the rearward sweep, flow is left to right.

In light of the results presented it can be inferred that changing the spanwise migration effect along the leading edge will reduce some of the energy required by the blade to overcome overall fluid momentum. It may also be useful to consider how the leading edge interacts with vortices around the leading edge as reported by Rangwala and Rai (1993) and Marshall and

Yalamanchili (1994a; 1994b). Blade sweep interrupts the spanwise migration and accumulation of low momentum fluid. The radial effect is a result of the rotational forces imposed and the impact of the blade on the fluid. This rotational effect is largely influenced by the Coriolis acceleration, which acts in the spanwise direction. A consequence of this is that a design must find a way to minimize or redirect the radial migration of low momentum fluids due to the Coriolis force.

The control of the shape of the leading edge profoundly influences the effects of the Coriolis forces and pressure distribution over the blade surfaces. With pressure distribution, the author simply means evolution of flow separations and reattachment that has been changed due to alterations to the leading edge geometry. In short, when the leading edge is used to control Coriolis forces, it also controls separation. This will be further discussed in the author's next paper Blade Geometry and Acoustics.

Design implications

To affect performance positively, one of the things a designer could do is understand the orientation of the forces that may affect performance such as the Coriolis force. The CFD results of figures 8 and 9 show the accumulation of low momentum fluids at the leading edge, while figure 7 shows no accumulation. Tests from previous studies, as previously reviewed, have shown that designs such as those of figure 7 are more efficient.

Conclusions

1. The turbulence interaction is manifested in the spanwise migration of low momentum fluid over the blade surface and along the leading edge.
2. The spanwise movement of fluid is due to the dominant component of the Coriolis force on the axial blade surface.
3. The forward sweep destructively interferes with the spanwise migration of fluid, in part by deflecting fluid away from the leading edge at the instant of leading edge and fluid interaction.

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